

Mother Tongue in Other Tongue Learning: The Third Way

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Abstract: The use of students' mother tongue (L1) in English (L2) teaching has long been a “to be or not to be” issue without persuasive research findings. Monolingual teaching pedagogy argues for Use-English-only policy with L1 excluded from the L2 classroom believing in the acquisition of L2 in the same way as L1 through massive exposure to the target language (L2). But bilingualism supported by the latest researches has recently questioned the validity and efficacy of English-Only policy and advocated for the judiciously limited use of the mother tongue of the students. Beyond this exclusion and the limited inclusion of the mother tongue, this paper investigates the possibility of “third way” of using Bangla, the mother tongue of the Bangladeshi learners, as an absolutely necessary tool in the English teaching pedagogy, and for this purpose, the study examines the perceptions and practices of the teachers and students at tertiary level in Bangladesh.

Keywords: Bangla-L1, Student attitude, Faculty belief, Tertiary level, Practicality

Introduction

Despite rapidly growing interest in English among the Bangladeshi learners, English teaching policy has still remained chaotically fluctuating because “Bangladesh has no explicit national policy of language” (Faquire, 2012). English, a compulsory subject from the first to twelfth grade, was taught exclusively through Grammar Translation Method (GMT) till 1990s when Bangla, the mother tongue (L1) of the teachers and the students, was the medium of conducting the English class, though ironically, without the use of

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English, the target language (L2). New textbooks along with the new methodology of teaching English was introduced in the 1990s (Islam and Ahsan, 2011) for the effective teaching of English by increasing the use of target language, which also failed due to the unavailability of efficient teachers in the field. English Language Teaching Improvement Project (ELTIP) established in 1998 (Haque, 2002, cited in Park, 2006) was another effort to improve the scenario. It introduced Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) in 2001 (Hasan and Akhand, 2001) and familiarized the teachers with the CLT approach by training the school and college teachers around the country. And this CLT approach brought in some limited use of English in the English language class and Bangla remains the language of English class as before.

The use of English in the English class has surged with the emergence of private universities in the late 90s in Bangladesh. With highly competitive job market in mind, the private universities attached highest importance to English teaching policy. Teachers equipped with IT (Information Technology) expertise and relevant language pedagogy have now appeared on the scene to teach the compulsory and optional English courses at undergraduate and graduate levels in all the departments. The university administrations' expectation of producing smart English-speaking graduate has inspired the faculty to conduct English-Only classes excluding Bangla. The students who have not heard much English spoken in their schools and colleges have now been in a class where almost no Bangla is allowed.

This journey from “all Bangla” to “no Bangla” in English language teaching policy at tertiary level had bewildering impact upon the students necessitating a research in order to explore the role of Bangla in learning and teaching process of English at the tertiary level. This study is an exploratory research into the positivity and, in some cases, pragmatic essentiality of the use of Bangla in the teaching of English at tertiary levels in Bangladesh.

Literature Review

The history of language pedagogy refers to “the long-standing controversies” (Stern, 1992) over the use of L1 in the teaching of L2. In the 16th century, bilingual teaching through translation from and into the L1 of the students was the indisputably accepted norm and practice. Classical languages such as Greek and Latin were taught through Grammar Translation Method over centuries (Larsen-Freeman, 1986). In the early nineteenth century as well, the bilingual Grammar Translation Method dominated L2 teaching.

Monolingual language teaching excluding the use of L1 dates back to the emergence of Reform Movement in the late nineteenth century with an aim to develop new language teaching principles (Richards and Rodgers, 2001). The role of L1 in the language teaching became controversial among the reformers. Gatenby (1965, cited in Phillipson, 1992) came up with monolingual ELT principles and J.S. Blackie (Hawkings, 1981, cited in Al-Nofaie, 2010) proposed a learning philosophy excluding the use of L1. Later, Krashen’s (1983) Monitor Model further contributed to the development of monolingual Direct Method by emphasizing the natural approach to language acquisition, where L2 is believed to be acquired through the same process as the L1 with immense exposure to L2 in the classroom. American involvement in the World War II brought about a significant change in the language pedagogy. The Americans developed the Audiolingual method in order to help the learners “to be able to use the language communicatively” (Larsen-Freeman, 1986). Like the Direct Method, it also focuses on the spoken language and forbids the use of L1 of the learners in the classroom. In 1970s, a new approach e.g. Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) developed in response to the failure of the Direct and Audiolingual methods. This pedagogy focusing mainly on the communicative competence allowed “limited and judicious use” (Schweers, 1999) of L1 in the L2 teaching process. Since then, there has been a tremendous

interest in and attention to the merit of the use of L1 in the L2 teaching pedagogy.

The monolingual approach suggests that “the target language ought to be the sole medium of communication implying [that] the prohibition of the native language would maximize the effectiveness of learning the target language” (Tang, 2002). As the learners in most of the educational environments get very limited or no chances of using the target language outside the classroom, classroom should be the society where the target language should be used in every possible occasion (Cross 1995, cited in Kafes, 2011) and the teachers are virtually the only sources of most of the linguistic input the learners can be exposed to (Brown 2001, cited in Kafes, 2011). So, “L1 languages should be excluded from the classroom” (Pennycook, 1994) and “language being studies should be ... sole medium of communication” (Gatenby, 1965).

Phillipson (1992) bases monolingual approach to English language teaching upon five dominant linguistic principles which he calls “five fallacies”:

- i. English is best taught monolingually. (Monolingual fallacy)
- ii. The ideal teacher of English is a native-speaker. (Native Speaker fallacy)
- iii. The earlier English is taught, the better the results. (Early-start fallacy)
- iv. The more English is taught, the better the results. (Maximum-exposure fallacy)
- v. If other languages are used much, standards of English will drop. (Subtractive fallacy)

The monolingual principles are, thus, understandably intended to increase the effectiveness of the L2 acquisition through the maximum use of the target language in the available situations and time span during the class. The approach seeks to exclude the L1

along with non-native L1 speaker teachers from the L2 classrooms in order to decrease, if not stop, any exposure to the L1, the mother tongue, of the learners because L1 interference is feared to be the main impediment to L2 learning (Cook, 2001).

“Since the publication of Phillipson’s (1992) *Linguistic Imperialism*, there has been a radical change in views regarding the issue of the use of L1 in the L2 classroom” (Ford 2009). Phillipson (1992) termed the monolingual principles as “fallacies” which are “rooted in the maintenance of colonial power and in misguided and negative beliefs about bilingualism” because all the five principles seem to “...serve the best interest of the native speaker teachers” (Weschler, 1997). Harbord (1992), therefore, criticizes the tenets and mentions the reactions in “certain parts of the world” against this linguistic hegemony of the “native speakers whose only object is to earn enough money to keep them in comfort until they moved on to their next destination”. But Skutnabb-Kangas (1994) terms this imposition of [L2] as a form of “linguistic genocide”, leading to the suppression of the other languages.

Pennycook (1994), Auerbach (2000) and Cook (2001) furthered this anti-monolingual attitude and argued for the facilitating and pragmatic necessity of the use of L1 in the L2 pedagogy because the use of L1 is a natural phenomenon. Cook (2001) rightly puts it, “Like nature, the L1 creeps back in, however many times you throw it out with a pitch-fork”. This is why even in English-Only US classrooms, “the use of the native language is so compelling that it emerges even when policies and assumptions militate against it” (Lucas and Katz 1994). And for the same reason, The UK National Curriculum still needs to remind teachers 120 years after the Great Reform, “The target language is the normal means of communication” (DES, 1990, cited in Cook, 2001).

The use of L1 in the L2 class is “a fundamental linguistic human right” (Canagarajah, 1999) and a democratic approach preferred by both the learners and the teachers. The study by Schweers (1999) with EFL students and their teachers in Spanish context shows that

“majority of the students (88.7%) felt that L1 should be used in their English classes and all the teachers reported using L1 in the class”.

The studies by Auerbach (1993), Atkinson (1993), Nation (2001) and Cook (2001) have, thus, contributed to the transition from “*Whether to use L1*” to “*when to use L1*” (Ford, 2009) in English learning-teaching process. Dornei and Kormos (1998) find that the L1 is used by L2 learners to compensate for communication deficiencies in the target language. Harbord (1992) listed three reasons for using L1 in the classroom: “facilitating teacher-student communication, teacher-student rapport and facilitating learning”. Cook (2001) states that the teachers should use L1 to convey meaning and organize class and the students can use it for scaffolding and for cooperative learning with fellow classmates. L1 use is the most effective tool while teaching new L2 vocabulary (Lado, Baldwin and Lobo, 1967, cited in Nation 2003). Harbord (1992) points out that “L1 use can save a lot of time and confusion”. Auerbach (1993, cited in Tang, 2002) not only acknowledges the positive roles of L1 use but also identifies the following situations for the L1 use: “classroom management, language analysis, presenting rules that govern grammar, discussing cross-cultural issues, giving instruction or prompts, explaining errors and checking for comprehension”.

Bangladeshi Perspective

Bangladesh is basically a monolingual country (Rasheed, 2012) with Bangla “spoken as the first language by 98 percent of the population” (Islam, 2013) for every day communication. So, the students hardly get any exposure to English outside the classroom (Mirza, Mahmud and Jabbar, 2012). The classrooms up to the X grade cannot offer exposure to much English because of the lack of qualified and competent teachers. Park (2006) finds that “more than half of the primary teachers hold SSC (Secondary School Certificate) or HSC (Higher Secondary School Certificate) as their

qualifications and “many secondary school teachers teach subjects, like English, which they did not study in their graduate courses”. “22.5 percent of teachers with commerce, science, social science and Madrasah background are teaching [English] language” (Park, 2006). Resultantly, the teachers cannot use English in the class for a considerable span of time, which eventually turns the English class a translation class without much use of English itself. The scenario does not change much in the college level even with the language teachers holding MA degree in English literature and language. The students continue to be deprived of exposure to English.

A number of these learners come to universities, both public and private, to study Business, Law, Economics, Pharmacy, Civil Engineering, Architecture, Fashion Designing, English and other job oriented subjects and find themselves lost as the medium of instruction here is English. The universities try to upgrade the newly admitted students with English language courses in first few semesters. And here lies the real challenge for the students. They have language teachers who are reluctant to use Bangla in English class in order to avoid stigmatization of inefficiency.

Research Rationale

The sharp contrasting journey from “all Bangla” in the school and college to seemingly “no Bangla” in the university is considered to be a major bar to the effective learning of English at the tertiary level in Bangladesh.

Unfortunately enough, despite bulk of research on L1 use in English classroom around the globe, the researchers have mostly “concentrated on General English and secondary education” (Cianflone, 2009). In recent years some attention has been paid to this issue at tertiary level, considering both students’ and teachers’ perspectives (Burden, 2001; Critchley, 1999, Schweers, 1999; Tang, 2000). In Bangladesh, the scenario is more frustrating as the

researchers tend to give attention to the use of Bangla in the school and college levels. Quite recently, there appeared some studies by Zaman (2009), Islam and Ahsan (2011), Chowdhury (2012), Mirza et al. (2012) on the L1 use in English class at tertiary level. Like others elsewhere, Bangladeshi researchers have also stressed the facilitating role of Bangla in the English pedagogy without going to the extent of necessary use of it in particular situations.

This study, like other ones, investigates the perceptions of the learners and the teachers towards the facilitating role of Bangla in English class at tertiary level but, *unlike others, it explores the pragmatic essentiality of the use of Bangla in English class.*

Methodology

Participants: The research was carried out among the two groups of participants – the students and the teachers. The questionnaire was distributed among 100 students of the 3rd and 5th semesters of the Department of English Language and Literature (ELL) at International Islamic University Chittagong (IIUC) and 92 of them returned the filled in questionnaire.

The questionnaire was distributed among the 25 teachers of three private universities and 20 of them responded with the filled in questionnaire. Out of 20 respondent faculties, 15 hold Master's Degrees in English Literature, 2 in Applied Linguistics, 2 in ELT and 1 in TESOL. Their professional position ranks from Lecturer to Associate Professor with teaching experiences ranging 2 to 12 years in the relevant field.

Data Collection: The study collected data through questionnaire and class recordings.

Questionnaire: Two separate sets of questionnaire were designed for the students and the teachers respectively for collecting quantitative data on their attitude and perception of the use of Bangla (L1) in the class.

The students' set of questionnaire aimed at investigating the perceptions of the students towards the use of Bangla in English class by themselves and by their teachers. The questionnaire explores into the frequency of the use of Bangla, its positive role and pragmatic use of Bangla with emphasis on the situations in which the use of Bangla is unavoidable both for the students and teachers.

The second set of questionnaire tried to investigate teachers' perception of the use of Bangla in English class. It also explored situations when the teachers and the students have no alternative to using Bangla for the desired acquisition of English.

Classroom Recordings: The researcher recorded four language classes of 50 minutes each at his department with the researcher being absent from the class by placing a mobile recorder in front of the teachers. Class recordings were preferred to class observation because presence of an observer might influence and change the normal interactions among the teachers and the students.

Procedures of Data Analysis: The study used both qualitative and quantitative analysis. The responses to the questionnaires for both the students and the teachers were sorted and counted manually. The classroom recordings were carefully listened to and the amount of the use of Bangla in the classroom recordings was manually noted down. The data thus received were analyzed using MS Excel 2007.

Results and Discussions

Data Analysis of the Questionnaires for the Students and teachers

Attitude towards the Use of Bangla: Table 1 shows that both the teachers and the students hold highly positive attitude towards the use of Bangla in the English language classroom. In response to the statement, "Bangla should be used in English language class",

95% of the teachers and 93% students agree with the use of Bangla at varying degrees. Only 5% teachers and 7% students are against the use of Bangla in the class while 15% teachers and 9% students want frequent use of Bangla. And the interesting finding to note is that the senior teachers and students tend to favor the use of Bangla more than the junior teachers and students. The only teacher against the use of Bangla is a private university graduate and has less than two years of experience and out of 7% students against the use of Bangla, 5% are from the 3rd semester and 1% is from the 5th semester but with English medium school background.

Table 1: Teachers and Students' attitude towards the use of Bangla

Attitude towards the use of Bangla	Teachers' Attitude		Student's Attitude	
	Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage
Always	0	0%	0	0%
Frequently	3	15%	8	9%
Moderately	3	15%	12	13%
Sometimes	13	65%	66	72%
Never	1	5%	6	7%
Total	20	100%	92	100%

Frequency of the use of Bangla in English class: The frequency of the use of Bangla both by the teachers and the students in the English language class is quite interesting. In response to the question, "How often do you/ your students use Bangla in English class?" significantly enough, 5% teachers and 7% students who were against the use of Bangla in the table 1 now admit that practically they use Bangla when needed. Frequent use of Bangla both by the teachers and the students now rises from 15% and 9% to 30% and 40% respectively.

The table 3 shows that 95% teachers and 100% students use Bangla in English language class at varying degrees. The students find that 38% of them and 35% of their teachers use Bangla "Frequently" while 5% teachers never use Bangla.

Table 2: Teachers' Perception of Prevailing Frequency of the Use of Bangla

Attitude towards the use of Bangla	Teachers' Attitude		Student's Attitude	
	Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage
Always	0	0%	0	0%
Frequently	7	35%	35	38%
Moderately	4	20%	13	14%
Sometimes	8	40%	44	48%
Never	1	5%	0	0%
Total	20	100%	92	100%

Table 3: Students' Perception of the Prevailing Frequency of the Use of Bangla

Attitude towards the use of Bangla	Teachers' Attitude		Student's Attitude	
	Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage
Always	0	0	1	5%
Frequently	6	30%	8	40%
Moderately	5	25%	5	25%
Sometimes	9	45%	6	30%
Never	0	0%	0	0%
Total	20	100%	92	100%

Facilitating Role of the use of Bangla: 90% teachers and 93% students appreciate the facilitating role of the use of Bangla in English language class. 25% teachers and 23% students believe its high positive role (Frequently) in the teaching/learning pedagogy while 10% teachers and 7% students think that Bangla does not contribute to effective teaching/learning of English.

Table 4: Facilitating Role of the use of Bangla

Facilitating role the use of Bangla	Teachers' Attitude		Student's Attitude	
	Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage
Always	0	0%	14	15%
Frequently	5	25%	21	23%
Moderately	4	20%	18	20%
Sometimes	9	45%	33	36%
Never	2	10%	6	7%
Total	20	100%	92	100%

Situations for using Bangla in English Class: The highest situations in which the teachers use Bangla in English class include explanation of grammar (27%) and unknown vocabulary and phrases (23%). The teachers also use Bangla for making the students confident (19%), checking the comprehension of the lesson taught (11%), for explaining difficult and cultural issues (10%), for managing and giving instructions to the class (6%). In only 4% situations, the teachers use Bangla for giving background knowledge and for explanation of the differences between Bangla and English grammar.

Figure 1: Situations for the teachers to use Bangla

The students (as in the figure 2) use Bangla in the highest situations (53%) for asking and answering questions in the class, 33% for feeling confident in the class and 14% for group and pair work.

Figure 2: Situations for the students to use Bangla

Situations of the essentiality of the Use of Bangla: In response to the query whether the teachers and the students encounter situations when they must use Bangla, both of them admit the essentiality of the situations in some particular cases. Table 5 shows that the teachers point out four essential situations for themselves while the students think the teachers are in fact found to use Bangla in five situations. The teachers find that they must use Bangla in 40% situations in the explanations of abstract ideas and cultural issues but the students point out that the teachers are seen essentially using Bangla in 24% situations for the purpose. Against teachers' perception of their 24% Bangla, the students find the teachers using 44% Bangla for the explanation of unknown words and complex sentences. The teachers believe that they must use Bangla in 24% situations for checking comprehension of the lesson while the students find the percentage to be 8%. While the students' finding of their teachers' use of Bangla for instructional and feedback purpose is 21%, the teachers themselves think that they only use Bangla at lower percentage of 17% situations. But the most interesting finding is that the teachers do not think they need to use any Bangla (0%) for conducting pair and group work, but the students find their teachers using Bangla for the purpose in 8% situations.

Table 5: Essential Situations for the Teachers to use Bangla

Situations	Teachers' Perception		Students' Perception	
	Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage
To explain unknown words and complex sentences	6	24%	84	44%
To Explain abstract ideas and cultural issues	10	40%	46	24%
To give instructions about the class assignments	4	16%	40	21%
To check comprehension of the lesson taught	5	20%	16	8%
To conduct pair and group	0	0%	6	3%
Total	25	100%	192	100%

The teachers find their students essentially using Bangla in 30% situations because they lack lexical competency while the students themselves think this essential situation to be at 31%. The teachers think that the students are bound to use Bangla in 35% situations because of the grammatical deficiency to make sentences while the students believe that it happens only in 29% situations. Assignment and feedback is the third situation of the essential use of Bangla in which the teachers think that the students use Bangla in 24% situations while the students believe they use 22% situations. Because of shyness in speaking English, the teachers find the students using Bangla in 11% situations while the students think they use Bangla in 18% situations.

Table 6: Situations for the Students to use Bangla

Situations for students	Teachers Perception		Students' Perception	
	Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage
Lack of lexical knowledge	14	30%	58	31%
Lack of grammatical knowledge	16	35%	54	29%
To get clear instructions about the assignments.	11	24%	40	22%
Shyness in using English in the class	5	11%	34	18%
Total	46	100%	186	100%

Data Analysis for the Class Recording

Class Recordings show that all of the four teachers use Bangla at considerable frequency and time in their English language classes according to their need. The teachers (in the Table 6) use Bangla for explaining unknown vocabulary and phrases, grammar, difficult concepts, social and cultural meanings, for managing the class, telling jokes, checking the comprehension and giving feedback. The researcher finds an interesting fact that the frequency of use of Bangla (L1) increases with the teacher's length of experience. For example, One of the teachers with 12 years of experience uses a considerable span of time (45%) in using Bangla (L1), while new teachers with 2- 5 years use less Bangla (L1) in English classes. One teacher is found obliged to use Bangla translation of the word, "well" in the sentence, "Well, We would start the program at 7 p.m.". Even the teacher uses equivalent meaning from the local dialect from Chittagong.

Table 7: Amount of Bangla used in English Class

Situations	Frequency	Percentage
To explain new / difficult / abstract	46	28%
To explain difficult concepts/cultural issues	34	21%
To explain grammar	32	20%
To check for comprehension of the lesson.	21	13%
To discipline / manage the class/ give	20	12%
To give background knowledge of the lesson	6	4%
To explain differences between L1 & L2	4	2%
Total	163	100%

The questionnaires and Class Recordings show that both the teachers and the students at tertiary level in Bangladesh use Bangla in English classes in varying situations and frequencies with a highly positive attitude towards it.

In response to the statement, "Bangla should be used in English class", 90% teachers and 92% students show positive attitude with 15% teachers and 9% students choosing the use of Bangla

“frequently”. The finding is consistent with the studies by Medges (1994), Dornyei and Kormos (1998), Schweers (1999) and Tang (2002). The present study reflects similar Bangladeshi research in the relevant field. Zaman (2003 cited in Islam & Ahsan, 2011) finds 56.23% subjects and Mirza et al. finds it to be 65% while Islam and Ahsan, (2011) finds it to be 70%. The rising support for the use of Bangla in Bangladeshi perspective reflects the growing awareness of our teachers and the teachers about the effective use of the mother tongue.

The study shows an interesting finding about the frequency of use of Bangla by the teachers and the students. While the teachers find that 100% of the teachers and the students need to use Bangla, the students find that 95% teachers and 100% students are in need of using Bangla in English class. The study conforms to the research by Islam and Ahsan (2011) showing that 92.5 subjects support the use of Bangla in English class.

90% teachers and 93% students are found to appreciate the use of Bangla in English language class as having facilitating contribution to teaching and learning pedagogy. This is in line with the research by Mirza et al. (2012) that shows 93.33 subjects acknowledging the facilitating role of Bangla.

The teachers and the students use Bangla in English class for various purposes at varying frequencies. Teachers’ purposes include explanation of difficult grammatical rules (27%), unknown vocabulary and phrases (23%), creating confidence among the students (19%), checking comprehension (11%), explaining difficult and cultural issues (10%), disciplining the class (6%) etc. The students use Bangla for asking and answering questions (53%), for confidence building in the class (33%) and for participating in the group and pair work (14%). The study supports the studies by Jingxia (2010) showing that 22.4% L1 is used for the explanation of grammar, 56% for unknown words and 4.8% for confidence building in the students.

The present study focuses on a concept of the essential use of Bangla in English class. Both the teachers and the students feel that there are occasions and situations when both of them have no alternative to using Bangla. The teachers point out four essential situations for themselves while the students think the teachers are in fact bound to use Bangla in five situations.

The findings in this research are consistent with the major recent studies discussed in the literature review. Besides showing the facilitating role of Bangla and its pragmatic use, the research has also proved that Bangla requires to be re-introduced into English language class at tertiary level as an essentially necessary teaching and learning tool without any feelings of stigmatization. Butzkamm (2003) right defines the role of mother tongue:

“We should finally free ourselves of a fundamental misconception and re-establish the more than two-thousand-year-old productive alliance between the mother tongue and foreign languages”

Conclusion

The present study shows that the use of Bangla in English Language class at tertiary level in Bangladesh is a prevalent practice preferred by the teachers and the students. Despite the CLT's buzzing warning of the danger of the overuse of Bangla in English class, the research suggests restoration of Bangla into English class with its due right to be an essential part of the language learning pedagogy in the situations when both the teachers and the students cannot help using Bangla. This pragmatic necessity and then essentiality of the use of Bangla started being felt and supported couples of years ago. Schweers (1999) encourages the use of mother tongue by allowing the “limited and judicious” use of the mother tongue because “it can aid and facilitate the learning and teaching” (Tang, 2002) of English. Cianflone (2009) comes up with Cole's (1998) suggestion “[the L1 use] can be considered an important learning device to suggest ‘equivalence’ or as a medium to avoid the teacher playing like ‘a

contortionist' in the struggle of keeping away from a simple L1 explanation". Al-Nofaie (2010) finds the use of mother tongue as "unavoidable and fundamental to L2 acquisition. Finally, Butzkamm (2007) confirms the essentiality of the use of mother tongue:

"Mother tongue support is thus an absolute necessity for the foreign language learner, and well-devised, provably effective bilingual techniques should be central techniques that all teachers should learn to master".

Recommendation

The study, therefore, recommends a "third way" (Canagarajah, 1999) that seeks to negotiate between the uses of Bangla and English in the English language class. While the use of and exposure to English in the class should continue, the use of mother tongue (Bangla in our case) must not remain a "a well-kept family secret,...a taboo subject, source of embarrassment" (Prodromou, 2002) and "an evasive manoeuvre...only to be used in emergencies" (Butzkamm, 2003). Rather, Bangla should be used whenever the teachers and the students feel the necessity of it as an essential helping hand. Islam & Ahsan (2011) rightly puts it:

"...when teachers feel that it is imperative for them to have the privilege of using Bangla in the English classes they should not hesitate to use it at that very moment. Likewise, when they find their students unable to express themselves in English for the lack of proficiency in speaking and that the use of Bangla could fulfill the students' need at the moment; they should allow the learners to use it".

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